

Effects of Charged/Polar Interfaces of various Surfactants on Photoredox Reaction of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$

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The effects of charged/polar interfaces of ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the efficiency of photo-induced intramolecular redox reaction of a cobalt(III) complex, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$, at two different wavelengths of exciting radiation have been investigated.

The study of photophysical processes and photochemical reactions in ordered molecular assemblies has added a new dimension to photochemical research. Amongst the various ordered molecular assemblies micellar systems have been extensively investigated. Since a micellar medium provides a novel environment for reactive solutes unlike those in homogeneous solutions, a thermal or photochemical reaction carried out in micellar media is influenced by the micellar environment which results in control/modification of reactivity. The salient features of micellar aggregates that influence the photochemical reactivity of inorganic complexes are cage and microviscosity effects, localisation and compartmentalisation effects and the effect of charged interface.¹

The present work is mainly concerned with the role of charged/polar 'host' interfaces in controlling the charge transfer photochemistry of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$. The efficiency of intramolecular photoredox reaction, as manifested in the quantum yields of Co^{2+} ($\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$) has been determined in pre-micellar and micellar solutions of six different surfactants in acetate-acetic acid buffers of three different pHs, viz. 3.72, 4.10 and 4.63.

Results and Discussion

Critical micelle concentration (CMC) values of the surfactants are given in Table 1. Results of photolysis of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]^{2+}$, expressed in terms of quantum

TABLE 1 - CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATION (CMC)* OF AQUEOUS MICELLAR-FORMING SURFACTANTS USED

Surfactant	CMC mM
Anionic	
$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{11}\text{OSO}_3 \text{Na}^+$ Sodium dodecylsulphate [SDS]	8.0
$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}\text{SO}_3 \text{Na}^+$ 1-Decanesulphonic acid, sodium salt	32.6
Cationic	
$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Br}$ Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide [C1AB]	0.92
$\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_{15}\text{N}^+\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Br}$ Hexadecylpyridinium bromide [CPyB]	0.75
Nonionic	
$\text{R}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2)_n\text{OH}$ $\text{R} = \text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}$, $n = 2, 3$ Polyoxyethylene(23)dodecanol [B11]-35]	0.06
$\text{R} = (\text{CH}_2)_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$, $n = 9, 5$ Polyoxyethylene-t-octylphenol [Iton X-100]	0.26

*CMC given are for aqueous solutions at 25 °C, 1 atm in the absence of any additive values taken from Refs. 2-4

yields of Co^{2+} , in surfactant-free aqueous solution are presented in Table 2. Quantum yields of Co^{2+} in pre-micellar and micellar solvents of different surfactant solutions are presented in Tables 3-8.

The experimental results can be interpreted in terms

of the following scheme for the reaction pathways :

Δ is the amount of light energy absorbed in excess of that required for homolytic dissociation. Uv irradiation leads to the population of ligand-to-metal charge transfer (LMCT) states^{5,6}, geminate pairs consisting of $\text{Co(NH}_3\text{)}_5^{2+}$ and Br are formed due to homolytic splitting of Co-Br bond. The efficiency of the electron transfer reaction is determined by the competition of diffusive separation and recombination reactions of radical pairs.

Effect of traces of surfactants on the quantum yield of Co^{2+} : The results indicate that the presence of a trace amount of any surfactant in solution (even at a concentration 100-fold lower than its CMC) raises the value of the quantum yield of Co^{2+} in comparison with the same quantity in pure aqueous (surfactant-free) solution.

On irradiation LMCT transition causes a decrease in the oxidation number of the central atom or in other words, the initial charge of the substrate is dispersed in the transition state. The rate of an electron transfer reaction is aided by nonpolar solvent if the initial charge of the substrate gets diffused in the transition state. The

TABLE 2 - PHOTOLYSIS OF $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$: QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN SURFACTANT-FREE AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS

Temp = 35°, Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer, Environment : homogeneous

Excitation wavelength nm	$\times 10^4$ [complex] mol dm ⁻³	pH	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
254	1.0	4.63	0.33
		4.10	0.32
		3.72	0.31
313	5.0	4.63	0.164
		4.10	0.154
		3.72	0.134

increased quantum yield of Co^{2+} in presence of traces of surfactants, suggests that the presence of a surfactant in aqueous solution brings about a diminution in solvent polarity and this is not unnatural as every individual molecule of any surfactant is composed of a large hydrocarbon moiety. In relatively high concentration of surfactants, other factors come into play affecting the quantum yield of Co^{2+} in diverse ways.

Quantum yield of Co^{2+} in micellar solution : The results summarised in Tables 3 and 6 reveal the following. (i) The quantum yield of Co^{2+} diminishes in moving from premicellar to micellar solutions of anionic surfactants, SDS and 1-decanesulphonic acid (ii) The quantum yield of Co^{2+} decreases sharply as the

TABLE 3 - QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN PREMICELLAR AND MICELLAR SOLUTIONS OF ANIONIC SURFACTANTS

Excitation wavelength = 254 nm, [Complex] = 1×10^{-4} M, Temp. = 35°, Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer

pH	Surfactant in the medium	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	Environment	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$		
4.63	SDS	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.45		
		1×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.46		
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.37		
		5×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.28		
		1×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.22		
		1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.40		
4.10	SDS	1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.30		
		5×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.26		
		1×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.21		
		1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.39		
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.29		
		5×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.24		
3.72	SDS	1×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.19		
		1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.41	
		6×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.35		
		6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.22		
		1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.39	
		6×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.33		
4.10	1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.21		
		6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.36		
		6×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.31		
		6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.19		
		3.72	1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.36
		6×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.31		
3.72	1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.19		

TABLE 4 – QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN PREMICELLAR AND MICELLAR SOLUTIONS OF CATIONIC SURFACTANTS

 Excitation wavelength = 254 nm, [Complex] = 1×10^{-4} M, Temp. = 35°, Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer

pH	Surfactant in the medium	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	Environment	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
4.63	CTAB	1×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.36
		1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.36
		1×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.36
		5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.35
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.32
4.10	CTAB	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.35
		1×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.33
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.30
3.72	CTAB	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.34
		1×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.30
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.27
4.63	CPyB	7.5×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.39
		7.5×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.36
		7.5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.33
4.10	CPyB	7.5×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.37
		7.5×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.35
		7.5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.31
3.72	CPyB	7.5×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.35
		7.5×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.33
		7.5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.29

concentration of SDS or 1-decanesulphonic acid increases in post-micellar solution. The same two trends have been observed, apparently in a less prominent way, for micellar solutions of nonionic surfactants Triton X-100 and Brij-35 (as evident from Tables 5 and 8).

In micellar solution, the complex ions (being positively charged) are bound to the negatively charged interfaces of anionic micelles and the solvent molecules (being polar) are highly structured in the microenvironment of the complex ions owing to the intense electric field of the charged aggregates. This factor leads to an enormous increase in the microviscosity of the environment. As a result, the diffusive separation of the radical pair is inhibited and the quantum yield of Co^{2+} decreases. The similarity in trends of results in presence of Triton X-100 and Brij-35 suggests that the

 TABLE 5 – QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN PREMICELLAR AND MICELLAR SOLUTIONS OF NONIONIC SURFACTANTS

 Excitation wavelength = 254 nm, [Complex] = 1×10^{-4} M, Temp. = 35°, Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer

pH	Surfactant in the medium	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	Environment	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
4.63	Triton X-100	2.4×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.37
		3.0×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.36
		2.4×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.28
4.10	Triton X-100	2.4×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.36
		3.0×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.32
		2.4×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.24
3.72	Triton X-100	2.4×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.35
		3.0×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.31
		2.4×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.23
4.63	Brij-35	6×10^{-6}	Premicellar	0.35
		6×10^{-5}	Micellar	0.34
		6×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.30
4.10	Brij-35	6×10^{-6}	Premicellar	0.33
		6×10^{-5}	Micellar	0.32
		6×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.29
3.72	Brij-35	6×10^{-6}	Premicellar	0.32
		6×10^{-5}	Micellar	0.30
		6×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.27

electrically neutral micelles of nonionic surfactants resemble the negatively charged micelles of anionic surfactants to some extent.

The results presented in Tables 4 and 7 indicate that the quantum yield of Co^{2+} decreases, not very sharply, even in micellar solutions of cationic surfactants, CTAB and CPyB. In micellar solution of CTAB or CPyB, the complex ions remain in the bulk of the solution as the micelles are all positively charged and the change in bulk viscosity (due to micellisation) is not large enough to bring about any observable change in the quantum yield of Co^{2+} . The noticeable decrease in $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ suggests that the following secondary thermal reaction may be partly responsible for the production of Co^{2+} ions

The diminution in $\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$ is due to the efficient trapping of Br_2 by positively charged micelles of CTAB and CPyB.

TABLE 6 – QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN PREMICELLAR AND MICELLAR SOLUTIONS OF ANIONIC SURFACTANTS

Excitation wavelength = 313 nm, [Complex] = 5×10^{-4} M, Temp. = 35°. Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer

pH	Surfactant in the medium	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	Environment	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
4.63	SDS	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.200
		1×10^{-2a}	—	—
		5×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.123
		1×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.090
4.10	SDS	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.180
		1×10^{-2a}	—	—
		5×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.119
		1×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.082
3.72	SDS	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.178
		1×10^{-2a}	—	—
		5×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.092
		1×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.074
4.63	1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.225
		6×10^{-2a}	—	—
		6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.101
4.10	1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.220
		6×10^{-2a}	—	—
		6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.098
3.72	1-Decane-sulphonic acid	6×10^{-3}	Premicellar	0.210
		6×10^{-2a}	—	—
		6×10^{-1}	Micellar	0.090

^aPhotolysis of 5×10^{-4} M complex in 1×10^{-2} M SDS and 6×10^{-2} M 1-decanesulphonic acid not tried as the systems became turbid.

Experimental

The complex $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Br}]\text{Br}_2$ was prepared according to the reported method⁷. The surfactants SDS, CTAB, Triton X-100, 1-decanesulphonic acid, CPyB and Brij-35 were of high purity grade.

The photolyses were carried out at 254 and 313 nm in quartz vessel. The 313 nm radiation was generated from a medium pressure mercury vapour (H-4) lamp and the 254 nm radiation generated from a low pressure mercury vapour lamp (Thermal Syndicate T/M5/594-110 W). The 313 nm radiation was isolated by using potassium chromate ($0.27 \text{ g} + 1.0 \text{ g Na}_2\text{CO}_3 \text{ dm}^{-3}$) filter.

TABLE 7 – QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN PREMICELLAR AND MICELLAR SOLUTIONS OF CATIONIC SURFACTANTS

Excitation wavelength = 313 nm, [Complex] = 5×10^{-4} M, Temp. = 35°, Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer

pH	Surfactant in the medium	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	Environment	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
4.63	CTAB	1×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.178
		1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.176
		1×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.169
		5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.152
4.10	CTAB	1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.133
		1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.167
		1×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.160
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.128
3.72	CTAB	1×10^{-4}	Premicellar	0.160
		1×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.150
		1×10^{-2}	Micellar	0.132
4.63	CPyB	7.5×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.198
		7.5×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.180
		7.5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.160
4.10	CPyB	7.5×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.190
		7.5×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.173
		7.5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.151
3.72	CPyB	7.5×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.180
		7.5×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.164
		7.5×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.142

TABLE 8 – QUANTUM YIELDS OF Co^{2+} IN PREMICELLAR AND MICELLAR SOLUTIONS OF NONIONIC SURFACTANTS

Excitation wavelength = 313 nm, [Complex] = 5×10^{-4} M, Temp. = 35°, Medium : acetate-acetic acid buffer

pH	Surfactant in the medium	[Surfactant] mol dm ⁻³	Environment	$\phi_{\text{Co}^{2+}}$
4.63	Triton X-100	2.4×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.176
		3.0×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.165
		2.4×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.123
4.10	Triton X-100	2.4×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.173
		3.0×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.146
		2.4×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.106
3.72	Triton X-100	2.4×10^{-5}	Premicellar	0.170
		3.0×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.152
		2.4×10^{-3}	Micellar	0.118

Table - 8 (Contd.)

4.63	Brij-35	6×10^{-6}	Premicellar	0.206
		6×10^{-5}	Micellar	0.190
		6×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.170
4.10	Brij-35	6×10^{-6}	Premicellar	0.198
		6×10^{-5}	Micellar	0.188
		6×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.165
3.72	Brij-35	6×10^{-6}	Premicellar	0.194
		6×10^{-5}	Micellar	0.178
		6×10^{-4}	Micellar	0.158

The temperature of the system was maintained at $35 \pm 1^\circ$ by circulating water and using thermostatic control device. The lamp output was observed before and after each run using ferrioxalate actinometry⁸. The photoreleased Co^{2+} was estimated by Kitson's method⁹.

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References

1. N. RAMNAIH, V. RAMESH and V. RAMAMURTHY, *J. Photochem.*, 1985, **31**, 75.
2. K. KALYANASUNDARAM, "Photochemistry in Microheterogeneous Systems", Academic, New York, 1987.
3. "Biochemical Organic Compounds for Research and Diagnostic Reagents", Sigma Chemical, 1993.
4. "Ordered Media in Chemical Separations", eds. W. L. HINZE and D. W. ARMSTRONG, ACS Symposium Series No. 342, American Chemical Society, Washington DC, 1987.
5. V. BALZANI and V. CARASSIHI, "Photochemistry of Coordination Compounds", Academic, New York, 1970.
6. C. H. LANGFORD and E. LINDSAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 1451.
7. "Inorganic Syntheses", ed. H. S. BOOTH, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1939, Vol. 1.
8. J. G. CALVERI and J. N. PITIS, "Photochemistry", Wiley, New York, 1966.
9. R. E. KITSON, *Anal. Chem.*, 1950, **22**, 664.

